

TECHNICAL SUMMARY

Irrigation Financing and Climate-Smart Agriculture

by Rishi Basak. Working Paper, 2017

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INTRODUCTION

Farmers in developing countries often struggle to secure the investment capital they need to set up and maintain effective irrigation systems – a central tenet of Climate-Smart Agriculture. This study discusses barriers to funding for small-scale projects, showcases examples of successful finance initiatives from around the world, and identifies opportunities for financiers, NGOs and government to collaborate more closely to improve access to loans.

WHY IS IRRIGATION FINANCE IMPORTANT?

Agriculture plays a significant role in the economies of most developing countries providing direct and indirect employment to the rural and urban labor force, but poor practice and demand pressures can put a strain on natural resources and negatively impact the environment.

Climate-smart agriculture (CSA) aims to sustainably:

1. Increase productivity
2. Make farming more resilient in the face of climate change
3. And reduce greenhouse gases from agricultural practices.

Adopting CSA practices, including irrigation technologies, can bring significant benefits to farmers:

- Irrigating agricultural land provides greater production certainty, compared to dryland farming (or rain-fed agriculture), offering farmers the opportunity to diversify and intensify output
- As weather variability worsens, leading to more frequent droughts, irrigation can help farmers

cope better with increased production risk.

Scenarios developed in the Comprehensive Assessment (de Fraiture et al. 2007) show that without substantial improvement in the productivity of rain-fed agriculture, and despite a considerable expansion of cropped area, irrigated area would have to increase to close to 500 million hectares globally to meet expected food demand, entailing a doubling of water use (Turrall et al. 2010)

There are many different types of irrigation: drip, sprinkler, surface, localized etc. The methods available to and chosen by farmers depend on myriad factors, including:

- Site conditions
- Existing infrastructure
- Availability of equipment
- And cost.

For irrigation to be financially viable, benefits - increased production and income - must outweigh up-front and ongoing costs. Studies show that most irrigation users are willing to pay for water if the

price is right and the quality of service acceptable.

In India, surface irrigation systems - canals and tanks - account for less than 25 million hectares of the total irrigated, compared to over 65 million hectares for groundwater irrigation - pumps and generators. Although the per hectare cost of groundwater irrigation is almost two to eight-fold the cost of surface systems, revenues still offset costs. A cost/benefit analysis of irrigation projects in China shows surface water irrigation can boost crop productivity and increase revenues by 1587 yuan per hectare (approximately \$230). Capital and operating costs varied significantly, depending on the system chosen – from 159 yuan per hectare (unlined canals), to 705 yuan per hectare (lined canals).

Many developing countries are realizing the benefits of irrigation extend far beyond agriculture:

- In South Africa, the government has instituted a National Water Policy, acknowledging the important role of irrigation in rural development.
- Data gathered in India found that 68% of irrigation benefits spillover to the non-farm economy.

But, lack of adequate finance continues to be the biggest barrier to the adoption of new agricultural technologies. And in many developing countries, there are few financial institutions that finance small-scale irrigation projects.

SUCCESSFUL IRRIGATION FINANCE

The Asian Development Bank's (ADB) Water Financing Program has funded more than 200 irrigation projects across its member countries, and aims to reach over 40 million farmers by 2020. Total investment stands at \$6.6 billion, with a further \$1.1 billion in the pipeline.

In Nepal, The ADB is financing a US\$24 million project focused on developing and improving small-scale irrigation systems in high-poverty, food insecure districts.

- The project will use participatory irrigation planning and management, building capacity at government-level for small-scale irrigation development
- Systems include surface water irrigation and shallow tube wells
- Access to microfinance and technical assistance along with electrification underpins the success of the project
- Commitment has been secured from water users associations to improve water management and agricultural practices, as well as maintaining irrigation systems
- The project has already led to an increase of 18 to 37% in cropping intensity.

In the Philippines, the farm cooperative PAICOR is partnering with the Land Bank of the Philippines

to offer financial (medium-term loans) and non-financial (processing and marketing) services to members with proven farming skills and good credit history.

The loans can be used for a wide range of agricultural activities, including land and equipment purchases.

Success factors include:

- Temporary farm takeovers in the case of serious arrears
- The provision of non-financial services e.g. marketing
- And increased compliance resulting from partnerships created by a membership program.

In 2003, The African Development Bank funded the Lower Usuthu Smallholder Irrigation Project

in Swaziland. The project was renewed in May 2016. Phase two involved \$63 million secured from several partners, including the European Investment Bank, the Kuwait Fund and the Arab Bank for Economic Development in Africa, the International Fund for Agricultural Development, as well as the National Government. The loan covers currency fluctuations as well as construction costs.

When completed, the project should:

- Irrigate 11,500 hectares of land to grow sugarcane
- Help smallholder farmers move from subsistence farming to small-scale commercial farming
- Increase food security and the incomes of over

2,000 rural households

- And help diversify farming for food and cash crops.

Kenya's commercial banks are increasingly active in providing credit to smallholder farmers for a wide range of activities, including irrigation. The Agricultural Finance Corporation is also funding two irrigation pilot schemes in the Tana River, which it hopes to replicate across the country.

Working with irrigation associations in **Bolivia**, who contribute a minimum of 10% of the investment cost (in cash or in-kind), and cover ongoing operation and maintenance costs, **The Inter-American Development Bank (IDB)** provided a \$34.3 million loan to fund the cost of construction, rehabilitation and project management. Technical assistance and training is also provided to improve irrigation practices and ensure the system is operated and maintained appropriately.

Bolivia's Caja Los Andes, a microfinance institution with over 24 branches, has a large agricultural portfolio, including loans for irrigation equipment. Finance is given for up to five years, at a monthly rate of 3% to 3.5%, with the repayment schedule adapted to the farmer's household income. Peer-group pressure helps reduce defaults - nonpayers are announced on local radio.

INVESTMENT OPPORTUNITIES

Public/private partnership

The private sector is playing an increasing role in financing irrigation with individual farmers and collectives in countries like China and India eager to address sporadic surface water supply, better manage water runoff, and gain control of their watering schedule driving demand for investment - an opportunity for local commercial banks to partner directly with governments in country-led initiatives.

Rural intermediaries

For small-scale irrigation programs to succeed, farmers need medium-term loans to service ongoing operating and maintenance costs, as well as working capital to finance up-front investment in equipment and construction. Rural financial intermediaries can play a key role in brokering lending.

Community trusts

Community Water Trusts (also known as Water Sharing Investment Partnerships) is a concept developed by The Nature Conservancy, and could be adopted more broadly. They generate returns for investors and promote sustainable water use by acquiring and managing a portfolio of water rights, either through direct purchase or by improving

irrigation efficiency. The water rights associated with any savings are transferred to the trust, and remaining rights leased to other water users. Private capital provides the funding. This can take the form of blended finance, with governments and philanthropic donations de-risking by covering first losses.

Blended finance model:

Source: (*The Nature Conservancy 2015*)

KEY CONSIDERATIONS FOR FUTURE SUCCESS

Involving farmers and other stakeholders in the project development phase leads to better planning and implementation, reducing demand for overly sophisticated technology.

Small-scale irrigation projects require provision of

technical support in order to be successful.

The benefits of irrigation extend beyond agriculture. From a public policy perspective, it makes sense to spread the cost. Commercial banks and other financial institutions should work more closely with governments to establish programs financed by all stakeholders: utilities, broader tax base etc. – not just farmers.

CASE STUDY - BASIX GROUP

The BASIX group is a partnership between a non-bank financial institution, an Indian commercial bank and an NGO, providing technical assistance and loans (via commercial and concessionary sources). Equity investors include:

- The Ford Foundation
- The International Finance Corporation
- The Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation
- And Triodos (an ethical bank based in the Netherlands).

BASIX has been promoting sustainable livelihoods for the rural poor through the provision of microcredit and technical assistance since 1996, and now operates in almost 40,000 villages across 18 states in India. It also provides consulting services in microfinance, institutional development and offers information technology solutions for microfinancing.

The group has a long history of involvement in irrigation projects. In the early 2000's, it conducted a pilot project in Andhra Pradesh to revive the abandoned lift irrigation infrastructure along the Krishna river, which has since been run as a program by the State's Irrigation Department.

The microcredit offered is for crop, irrigation and land development. Loan repayment schedules vary by crop and cropping season, as well as household cash flow. Most of the agricultural loans they provide are payable in one to three installments over a period of six to 11 months. Loans for irrigation are for up to three years, at 24% per annum. Technical assistance is offered to farmers for US\$7 per year (450 rupees) and includes marketing and agricultural advice tailored to the crop being farmed and the technology purchased through the loan.

So far, BASIX has offered over US\$30 million in micro-loans (averaging US\$160 per loan), reaching more than 300,000 smallholder farmers. Default rate is low, with 98.5% paying back their loans within the agreed repayment schedule. BASIX is building on its experience in providing agricultural credit to smallholder farmers and is extending its financial services to larger farmers and agribusinesses, and hopes to reach up to three million farmers in the coming years.